

mosaic

Data Management plan

Deliverable No. D1.1

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Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

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Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable is to become the support tool for the project consortium in managing data collected during the duration of the project. This Data Management Plan (DMP) presents a data summary, describes the provisions for sharing FAIR data, and addresses data security. It also addresses the allocation of resources and data management roles and responsibilities.

The DMP will be constantly updated throughout the life of the project, including before the first review meeting and at the end of the project before the final review. It will also be reviewed if there are any significant changes that affect the project, such as changes in relevant regulation, necessary adaptations to research methodologies, or any other developments that occur that affect data management. This deliverable includes a guide for the data collection, storage and the ongoing and future activities of handling data, during and even after the project is completed. Detailed information included in the DMP are: data management lifecycle for all data sets that will be collected, processed or generated by the project. Further, the methodology and standards are outlined and it is explained whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved.

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	2
Deliverable Information	3
1. Introduction.....	5
2. Legal framework.....	6
2.1 The EU Personal Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).....	6
2.2 Open Access in Horizon 2020	6
3. FAIR data	8
3.1 Overview.....	8
3.2 Data Summary	9
3.3 Data Collection	10
3.3 Data Processing	11
3.4 Data Storage	13
3.5 Data Sharing	13
3.6 Data Security	14
4. Conclusions and responsibilities	16
4.1 Conclusions.....	16
4.2 Responsibilities regarding data management	16

1. Introduction

MOSAIC is a 3-year long project that started in January 2021. Drawing upon the richness of SwafS experiences so far, MOSAIC's research will lead to the assessment of effective instruments applicable to successful co-creation approaches in quadruple-helix Open Innovation pathways. While doing so, the MOSAIC consortium will define and assess indicators to measure impacts and transformative changes that are specific to this particular context, generating scientific publications as well as toolkits to be further used within future SwafS-like initiatives and beyond. Pilot actions in the cities of Brussels and Milan will test MOSAIC's methodological approach and research actions throughout the project. The piloting process will produce concrete instruments and recommendations, to be replicated in further European cities and regions willing to engage in mission-oriented approaches via quadruple helix collaboration, but also to enrich the work of Horizon Europe researchers and stakeholders more broadly.

MOSAIC research activities that involve participants are described in WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP6. The preliminary list of data collection tools and methods that will be used in MOSAIC's research activities is the following:

- document analysis, mobilizing published material
- visualizing project meta-data, mobilizing the CORDIS database
- digital surveys
- interviews
- participatory workshops
- discussions and learning sessions

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 is a brief overview of FAIR data, the legal framework, including the EU regulation on personal data protection (GDPR), the H2020 provisions for open access to research data
- Section 3 discusses the different data usage scenarios and the key issues to be examined in relation to each scenario. These issues include decisions on e.g. data anonymization, privacy and security protection measures, licensing, etc.
- Section 4 is the conclusion, with a description of how the document will be maintained and updated in the future.

2. Legal framework

This section gives a brief overview of the key references in regard to making up the DMP external context. The next paragraphs respectively deal with:

1. The General Data Protection Regulation, which came into force in May 2018;
2. The terms of the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) the MOSAIC consortium has adhered to;

2.1 The EU Personal Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 sets out the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) framework in the EU, notably concerning the processing of personal data belonging to EU citizens by individuals, companies or public sector/non-government organisations, irrespective of their localization. It is therefore important that the MOSAIC consortium takes GDPR into consideration in its data management. GDPR was adopted on 27th of April 2016 and became enforceable on 25th of May 2018 after a two-year transition period. The regulation has replaced the previous Data Protection Directive (95/46/EC) and its national implementations. Being a regulation, not a directive, GDPR does not require Member States to pass any enabling legislation but is directly binding and applicable. The GDPR provisions do not apply to data processed by an individual for purely personal reasons, or activities carried out at home, provided there is no connection to a professional or commercial activity. When an individual uses personal data outside the personal sphere, for socio-cultural or financial activities, for example, then the data protection law has to be respected. On the other hand, the legislative definition of personal data is quite broad, as it includes any information relating to an individual, whether it relates to his or her private, professional or public life. It can be anything from a name, a home address, a photo, an email address, bank details, posts on social networking websites, medical information, or a computer's IP address. It is worth noting that the specific requirements of GDPR for privacy and security will be separately dealt with in other MOSAIC Deliverables (such as D7.1 : H - Requirement No. 2; D7.2 : POPD - Requirement No. 3).

2.2 Open Access in Horizon 2020

The European Commission (EC) has launched in H2020 a flexible pilot for open access to research data (ORDP), aiming to improve and maximise access to and reuse of research data generated by funded Research & Development (R&D) projects, while at the same time taking into account the need to balance openness with privacy and security concerns, protection of scientific information, commercialisation and intellectual property rights (IPR). This latter need is aided by an opt-out rule, according to which it is possible at any stage - before or after the GA signature - to withdraw from the pilot, but legitimate reasons must be given, such as IPR/privacy/data protection or national security concerns.

The ORDP has been extended to cover all H2020 thematic areas by default. This has particularly generated the obligation for all consortia to deliver a Data Management Plan (DMP), in which they specify what data the project will generate, whether or not it will be freely disclosed, how it will be

made accessible for verification and reuse, and how it will be curated and preserved. The ORDP applies primarily to the data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications. Other data can however be provided by the beneficiaries of H2020 projects on a voluntary basis. The costs associated with the Gold Open Access rule, as well as the creation of the DMP, can be claimed as eligible in any H2020 grant.

3. FAIR data

3.1 Overview

A good DMP under H2020 should comply with the FAIR Data Handling Principles. Sharing data in line with the FAIR principles requires that the data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). The European Commission (2016) considers the FAIR principles fulfilled if a DMP includes the following information:

- A. “The handling of research data during and after the end of the project”
- B. “What data will be collected, processed and/or generated”
- C. “Which methodology and standards will be applied”
- D. “Whether data will be shared/made open access”, and
- E. “How data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project)”.

The following sections of the document address the FAIR principles:

3.1 Data summary (typologies and contents of data collected and produced)

3.2 Data collection (which procedures for collecting which data)

3.3 Data processing (which procedures for processing which data)

3.4 Data storage (data preservation and archiving during and after the project)

3.5 Data sharing (including provisions for open access)

In accordance with Guidelines on FAIR Data management in Horizon 2020 (European Commission, 2016), the objectives of the DMP are:

- To identify the datasets that MOSAIC will produce
- To define how these datasets will be made ‘FAIR’ (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable)
- To define the allocation of resources (costs and responsibility) for data management during and after the project
- To define procedures for data security (including data recovery as well as safe storage) during the project and for long term preservation.

In this section, the different data usage scenarios will be discussed in detail, in relation to data summary, data collection, data processing, data storage, data sharing, and finally data security. In this way, the data management lifecycle of the MOSAIC will be presented in full.

The three scenarios that make up the MOSAIC data management lifecycle are:

1. Original data produced by the MOSAIC consortium and/or individual members of it (e.g. the questionnaires, transcripts and recordings of interviews, focus groups and reports from co-design and co-creation workshops);
2. Existing data already in possession of the MOSAIC consortium and/or individual members of it prior to the beginning of the project (see Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement);
3. Existing data sourced/procured by the MOSAIC consortium and/or individual members of it during the project's timeline.

It is also important to note that the datasets handled within the three above scenarios can belong to either of these three categories:

- Confidential data (for business and/or privacy protection)
- Anonymised and Public data (these two aspects go hand in hand)
- Non anonymised data (the residual category).

3.2 Data Summary

The following table summarises the typologies and contents of data collected and produced during the project timeline.

	Confidential data sets	Anonymised, Pseudonymised and Public data sets	Non Anonymised data sets
Original data produced by the MOSAIC consortium	<p>Any possible sensitive data from the surveys, interviews and the participatory workshops.</p> <p>Personal data of people participating in our research, such as email and mail addresses and phone numbers.</p> <p>New contacts established.</p>	<p>Summaries of questionnaires/interviews/ reports from workshops.</p> <p>End user data, stakeholders and policy makers data on public display.</p> <p>Contact data within Deliverables.</p>	<p>Photos/videos shot of adults during public events and project workshops</p> <p>Audio recordings (e.g. Zoom) and interviews.</p> <p>Data in the project Internal repositories.</p>
Existing data sourced/procured by the MOSAIC consortium	Data embedded in some of the Background knowledge (see	Data embedded in some of the Background knowledge (see Consortium Agreement).	N/A

and/or partners	Consortium Agreement). Contact databases.		
Existing data already in possession of the MOSAIC consortium and/or partners	Raw data in possession of the pilots or of any third party involved in the pilots.	Free and open data (including from scientific and statistical publications).	N/A

All non-Confidential data collected and produced during the project timeline will be managed as follows:

- For any photos/videos shot during the project internal events and meetings, as well as public events related to the project, it is crucial to collect an informed consent form all the participants, with an explicit disclaimer in case of intended publication of those personal images on e.g. newspapers, internet sites, or social media groups. This will bring the data back into the Confidential category, where it is legitimate to store and/or process it for legitimate reasons.
- For any audio recordings stored, e.g. in the project's official repository (currently NexCloud) or in individual partners' repositories, care must be taken of the risk of involuntary disclosure and/or the consequences of misuse for any unauthorised purpose. Same goes for the personal data of each partner in the consortium.
- Informed consent forms must be signed (or electronically signed) by all participants taking part in questionnaires, interviews, focus groups and workshops. Detailed procedures on informed consent and their storage will be described in the deliverables for WP7.
- Informed consent is also required when using available contacts (be they pre-existing to the project or created through it) to disseminate information via e.g. newsletters or dedicated emails. In this respect, the GDPR provisions are particularly binding and must be carefully considered.

3.3 Data Collection

The following table summarises the procedures for collecting project related data.

	Confidential data sets	Anonymised and Public data sets	Non Anonymised data sets
Original data produced by the MOSAIC consortium	Surveys, interviews, participatory workshops, meetings	Newsletters Reports Publications	A/V conferencing

	with stakeholders, evaluation sessions	Springer brief Open Access repositories	Systems and Internal repositories
Existing data sourced/procured by the MOSAIC consortium and/or partners	Seamless access and use during project execution	Seamless access and use during project execution	N/A
Existing data already in possession of the MOSAIC consortium and/or partners	Licensed access and use during project execution	Free, open access and use during project execution	N/A

Data will be collected in both paper and digital forms (CSV, PDF, Word, xls spreadsheets and textual documents will be the prevalent formats). For the data collected via paper, these documents will be scanned by the partners and third parties and stored digitally. Original copies will be destroyed within 2 months of being collected. In case of audio/video recordings and images, the most appropriate standards will be chosen and adopted (such as .gif, .jpg, .png, .mp3, .mp4, .mov and .flv). Website pages can be created in .html and/or .xml formats.

Research data in the MOSAIC project is primarily generated by the members of the Consortium. This data mainly takes the form of digital surveys, interviews, participatory workshops. Research data generated throughout the project includes primarily qualitative material, as well as some quantitative information, e.g. information about workshop participants. Curated and anonymised materials will be made publicly available. These include the following:

- Data gathering and analysis templates
- Templates and guidelines for evaluation data gathering and analysis; Completed templates from each pilot containing evaluation material from workshops and other activities/events carried out in the “mirror ecosystems”.

3.3 Data Processing

The following table summarises the procedures for processing MOSAIC related data that can be envisaged at this project’s stage.

	Confidential data sets	Anonymised and Public data sets	Non Anonymised data sets
Original data produced by the MOSAIC consortium	Anonymisation Analyses/ Visualisation	Qualitative and quantitative Evaluation Analyses/ Visualisation	Anonymization

Existing data sourced/procured by the MOSAIC consortium and/or partners	Anonymisation Statistical evaluation	Analyses/Visualisation Qualitative and quantitative Evaluation	N/A
Existing data already in possession of the MOSAIC consortium and/or partners	Anonymisation Statistical evaluation	Analyses/Visualisation Qualitative and quantitative evaluation	N/A

Partner institutions are left free to adopt their preferred suite and working tools (such as e.g. Microsoft Office for PC or Mac, Apple's iWork and OpenOffice or equivalent). However, the following tools are the ones mainly used by the consortium:

- NexCloud's shared productivity tools (OnlyOffice) are used for the cocreation of outputs by multiple authors
- Adobe Acrobat or equivalent software is used to visualise/create the PDF files
- Photoshop or equivalent software are used to manipulate images
- Internet browsers (such as Mozilla Firefox, Google Chrome, Apple Safari and Microsoft Internet Explorer) are used to navigate pages, including the management and maintenance of social media groups
- Zoom is the selected tools for audio/video conferencing, which may also serve to manage public webinars
- Survey tools like Limesurvey, Google Forms (or alternative) are used for the administration of online surveys with remotely located participants
- Dedicated YouTube/Vimeo channels can help broadcast the video clips produced by the consortium to a wider international audience, in addition to the project website
- Mailchimp or equivalent software is helpful to create, distribute and administer the project newsletters and the underlying mailing lists.

At the moment, email as well as and conference calls via Zoom are used for the consortium internal communication flow.

For research data collected and generated in the project, a fit-for-purpose file naming convention will be developed in accordance with best practice for qualitative data, such as described by the UK Data Archive (2011). This will involve identifying the most important metadata related to the various research outputs. Key information includes content description, date of creation, version, and location of where data was created.

3.4 Data Storage

The following table summarizes the procedures for storing project related data, during and after the MOSAIC lifetime, and the most frequently used repositories.

	Confidential data sets	Anonymised and Public data sets	Non Anonymised data sets
Original data produced by the MOSAIC consortium	Individual partner repositories. Common project repository (the current one is NextCloud).	Zenodo. Project website, partner websites, social media,	Individual partner repositories. Common project Repository (the current one is NextCloud).
Existing data sourced/procured by the MOSAIC consortium and/or partners	Individual partner repositories. Specific software Repositories.	Project website, partner websites, social media, Zenodo or other, depending on the choice of the partner owning the data.	N/A
Existing data already in possession of the MOSAIC consortium and/or partners	Individual partner repositories. Third party repositories Cloud repositories.	Project website, partner websites, social media, Zenodo.	N/A

NextCloud is the selected tool for MOSAIC data and information repository. This includes both the project deliverables (including relevant references utilised for their production or generated from them as project publications, e.g. journal articles, conference papers, e-books, manuals, guidelines, policy briefs, toolkits etc.) and any other related information, including relevant datasets.

Additionally, Stickydot will make sure that the official project repository periodically generates back-up files of all data, in case anything may get lost, corrupted or become unusable at a later stage (including after the end of the project). The same responsibility goes to each partner for the local repositories utilised by them (in some cases, these are handled by large organisations such as universities; in others, by small organisations or even personal servers or laptops). All files containing personal data will be stored in encrypted and password-locked files. Access to these files will be limited to authorised project personnel.

Datasets may also be stored on the following open access repositories such as OpenAIRE/Zenodo.

3.5 Data Sharing

Data sharing will be a very important aspect of the MOSAIC project, however it needs to be ensured that it is done in a useful and legitimate manner. When sharing, it is of utmost importance to keep in mind, not only the prescriptions and recommendations of extant rules and norms (including this DMP),

as far as confidentiality and personal data protection are concerned, but also the risk of voluntary or involuntary transfer of data from the inside to the outside of the European Economic Area (EEA).

	Confidential data sets	Anonymised and Public data sets	Non Anonymised data sets
Original data produced by the MOSAIC consortium	Personal email communication. Shared repositories.	Project website Zenodo	N/A
Existing data sourced/procured by the MOSAIC consortium and/or partners	Personal email communication. Shared access to software repositories	Project website Open access repository	N/A
Existing data already in possession of the MOSAIC consortium and/or partners	Personal email communication. Shared repositories.	Project website Open access repository	N/A

We intend to make curated research data coming from project accessible. This data may be useful for researchers, practitioners and others wishing to duplicate or adapt the MOSAIC model. In regard to how long is the intention that the data remains re-usable, we will adhere to the standard of the chosen repositories for the project.

3.6 Data Security

Data is shared between project partners and stored in a collaborative online working platform (NextCloud) during the project's lifetime. NextCloud is provided by SD as project coordinator. SD have commissioned BeByte srl to provide the NextCloud solution, which is based on OmniOS dedicated servers, hosted in OVH facilities at Gravelines, France. ZFS, OmniOS' native file-system, combines a volume manager and file-system with strong data-integrity protection and allowing encryption at block level as well. The GDPR compliant storage is itself based on Nextcloud, whose different components are running in lightweight OmniOS or Linux virtual containers without the overhead of a traditional hypervisor. For better data safety, Nextcloud Files delivers powerful encryption capabilities and a built-in rule-based File Access Control, meaning even the Server System Administrator cannot have access to those sensible data. Besides European location, our Nextcloud implemented solutions meet all GDPR requirements at both application and OS levels.

Uncurated and unanalysed material created during the project is stored locally by the MOSAIC partners according to their institutional data management and storage guidelines (see D7.1 and D.7.2). All final versions of evaluation data collected in the project and analysis outputs of this material will be saved in a standardised filing system with dedicated naming conventions. Consent forms will be kept beyond the end of the MOSAIC project as detailed in D7.1 and D7.2. Additional research data such as personal

notes, unused photos and video clips etc. will be safely deleted and discarded after the end of the project.

4. Conclusions and responsibilities

4.1 Conclusions

This Data Management Plan (DMP) in fulfilment of the requirements of WP1 has gathered together all the information regarding legal frameworks and GDPR, and has described how the MOSAIC consortium will align with the principles of FAIR data handling according to the EC requirements (and that the MOSAIC consortium and individual partners and third parties are bound to respect). It has also summarised the key aspects of data collection, processing, storage and sharing (the typical contents of a DMP) within the proposed data lifecycle elements and particularly highlighting - first and foremost, some key aspects of data management that go beyond the operational link with open access and interfere with privacy and security policies.

It is hoped that the DMP will enable all partners and third parties to understand the different actions required when handling data of different natures, and how to store and share it securely, in keeping with the EC requirements.

The DMP will be maintained and updated by the project coordinator in consultation with the Executive Board. Updates will be done according to the planned schedule and when needed due to changes in consortium policies, research methodology or other significant developments which affect the DMP.

4.2 Responsibilities regarding data management

The responsibilities for the data management are distributed and controlled as follows:

Data collection, storage and backup:

The partners and third parties who collect data (e.g. surveys, interviews and workshops). The responsibilities also include taking care of data security and personal data protection. Project partners who receive data from data collectors for project evaluation (UNI EIFFEL, SoScience) have the same obligations.

Metadata production in view of depositing the research data:

The partners and third parties based on guidelines provided by the project coordinator (SD) and leader of WP2 and WP6 (UNI EIFFEL). They will be provided with templates for the tasks involving data, which they will be required to fill in. This will ease and ensure consistency of the data provision, which will be controlled by the project coordinators.

Data deposition and sharing:

The project coordinators (SD), involving individual partners where further information or clarification is required (e.g. with regard to content authors or contributors, related material).

Responsibilities in general:

Each partner or third party is obliged to respect and follow the rules of the Grant Agreement and the Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020 (European Commission 2017). Support by the project coordinator or another partner in following the rules does not transfer these obligations to the supporting partner.

